

Moth-eye mimetic cytocompatible bactericidal nanotopography: a convergent design

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Abstract

The rapid emergence of antibiotic resistant bacteria has prompted the need for radically different approaches to combat bacterial infections. Among these, bioinspired surface topographies have emerged as an effective sustainable strategy to deter bacterial infection. This study demonstrates the bactericidal activity and cytocompatibility of the moth-eye mimetic topography produced by thermal polymer nanoimprinting. The moth-eye topography was found to have bactericidal capabilities against Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria. Electron microscopy imaging revealed the bactericidal effect caused by mechanical rupture of the bacteria wall inflicted by the topography on the adhered cells. The cytocompatibility of the surfaces was evidenced by assessing the proliferation and morphology of keratinocytes cultured on the nanotopography. The technology meets important needs in medical implant technology for materials that not only have good biocompatibility but also antibacterial properties for reducing the risk of infections and related health complications.

Introduction

Bacterial infection is a widespread problem impacting severely the health and the economy of our society. In particular, healthcare associated infections resulting from invasive medical devices such as catheters, implants or prosthetics are still important causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Among these, surgical onsite infections are the most severe health problem. Despite the high levels of hygiene, sterilization protocols and antibiotic prophylaxis, implant associated infections are still the cause of the most devastating complications in surgery with a prevalence from 2 to 40% depending on several risk factors and the type of implant [1]. These infections pose a significant threat to human health because bacteria proliferate on the surface of these artificial materials into biofilms which are extremely resilient to treatment. Generally, implant infection leads to implant removal with the associated increase in morbidity to the patient and in some cases, a risk of mortality altogether with huge costs [2].

A wide range of antibacterial surfaces have been developed by applying non-adherent or antifouling coatings, biocides or antibiotics [3]. However, these strategies are frequently temporary as the active mol-

ecules are depleted and in some cases fail, contributing to infection resistance. An additional shortcoming is the development of bacteria resistance by biocides and the persistence of these in the environment contributing to the emergence of resistant strains. To overcome both these issues, the obvious and most effective approach would be prophylactic, that is to avoid the proliferation and infection of bacteria before it happens by methods that do not generate resistance. This is precisely what nature does; nature has evolved several chemical and physical strategies for protection against bacteria without any known resistance. Many efforts have been attempted to develop bioinspired antibacterial surfaces and particularly natural bactericidal topographies have received a great attention. Two main approaches have been followed. One is based on mimicking topographies that reduce bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation [4–6] and the other is focused on mimicking natural bactericidal surfaces [7–9]. The best known natural bactericidal surface is the cicada wing nanotopography. This biological topography has demonstrated to produce a bactericidal effect against Gram negative bacteria [10–12]. The gecko skin nanotopography has also shown a bactericidal effect against Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria [13, 14]. Furthermore, the dragon-

fly, damselfly and planthopper nanostructured wings have shown to be effective against both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria [15–17]. A summary of the biomimetic bactericidal approaches described so far can be found in recent extensive reviews [18–20]. In addition to these biomimetic surfaces; herein we study the bactericidal effect of the moth-eye mimetic nanoprotusions. The mimetic moth-eye topography has been described and studied as a natural antireflective surface [21]. However, the study of the bactericidal activity of this natural surface has not been undertaken before. This pattern of nanocone type of features appearing in several unrelated species with the same antibacterial mode-of-action may suggest that these nanostructures are result of a convergent evolution.

Bioinspired antibacterial surfaces have been replicated on different synthetic materials. Cicada wing topography has been reproduced on polymer and titanium surfaces and they have demonstrated to be effective against Gram negative bacteria [6, 8, 22]. Inspired topographies of the dragonfly wing have been successfully reproduced on silicon [7, 23], titanium [18, 24, 26] and diamond [25] and demonstrated to be bactericidal against Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. Polymer replicas of the nanotipped hairs of the gecko skin have been proven to be effective against Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria [14, 27].

The approaches reported to fabricate antibacterial topographies vary depending on the base material of interest. Chemical techniques such as alkaline hydrothermal process have been utilized to produce nanoneedles in titanium [24, 26], physical techniques such as reactive ion etching have been employed to produce black silicon nanoneedles [7, 9] and nanoimprinting to replicate cicada inspired topographies on polymer [6, 8]. Nanoimprinting is a cost effective nanofabrication technique that replicates micro and nanostructures with high precision and resolution on a large range of polymers, making this technique suitable to produce antibacterial surfaces onto a variety of polymer surface at large scale.

Herein we present a study of the bactericidal properties of a moth-eye mimetic polymer topography produced via polymer nanoimprinting. The bactericidal effect of the imprinted topography is evidenced against three different bacteria frequently involved in biofilm-associated infections including the Gram-positive pathogen *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and Gram-negative *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*) and *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*). Furthermore, the cytocompatibility of the topography towards human keratinocytes (HaCaT) is investigated through studies of proliferation capability and spread morphology of the HaCaT cells seeded on the nanocone topography. HaCaT cells have been used as *in vitro* model to assess the biocompatibility of polymeric scaffolds for skin implants [28–30]. Keratinocytes were chosen as *in vitro* model due to their role in epidermal tissue regeneration and wound healing [31, 32] for the integration of percutaneous devices [33].

The results presented in this study indicate that the moth-eye mimetic polymer topography is a broad spectrum non-resistant causing bactericidal surface that at the same time supports mammalian cell growth and proliferation making these surfaces attractive for tissue engineering and bio-implant applications.

Methods

Moth-eye mimetic topography fabrication

The topography was fabricated on Poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA). Initially, PMMA thin films were produced on glass cover slips (18 mm in diameter). Prior to that, the glass cover slips surfaces were activated with oxygen plasma (Tepla 600) at 300 W for 5 min, to improve the adhesion between polymer and glass. On the surface, a solution of PMMA (Mw 120.000, Sigma Aldrich) on toluene (7.5 wt%) was spin coated at 1000 rpm for 1 min and subsequently, the films were annealed at 100 °C. The nanocone structures were created by a thermal nanoimprint process. Initially, a working mold with the moth-eye topography was prepared. This was obtained by replication of a master nickel mold (HT-AR-02) procured from Temicon using two layers of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS). First, hard PDMS (h-PDMS) (PP2-RG07, Gelest) was mixed (1:1 following manufacturer instructions) and casted onto the nickel mold and after 30 min standing for the filling of the cavities, the mold was spun (1000 rpm for 1 min). Subsequently, the h-PDMS was partially cured in an oven for 10 min at 80 °C. After that, a soft PDMS (Sylgard 184, Dow Corning) precursor and initiator were mixed, degassed and casted onto the partially cured h-PDMS layer and finally cured in an oven at 80 °C for 24 h. Lastly, the mold was peeled off and kept in a clean room environment. Using the replicated working molds, the prepared PMMA films were imprinting by pressing these molds at 170 °C at 45 bar or pressure for 5 min using an EITRE3 Nano Imprint Lithography system (Obducat). The polymer-mold assembly was cooled down to 70 °C before the pressure was released and the de-molding was performed. The topography of the substrates was imaged by scanning electron microscope (SEM) using an Auriga FIB-SEM system (Zeiss) and atomic force microscopy (AFM) using a Multimode 8 AFM system with a Nanoscope V controller (Bruker). For the measurements a rotated tip (MPP-11120-10, Bruker) with a nominal radius of 8 nm and spring constant $N = 40 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ was used.

Moth-eye surface wettability

The static contact angle measurements were performed using an optical tensiometer (Attension Theta, Biolin Scientific) using a droplet volume of 3 μl deposited on the surface by a dispenser. The static contact angles were measured by adjusting the drop profile to a Young–Laplace curve.

Bacteria culture and Live/Dead® BacLight™ viability assays

E. coli (CECT 516), *P. aeruginosa* (CECT 4628) and *S. aureus* (RN 4220) (Spanish Type Culture Collection, University of Valencia) were used to assess the bactericidal properties of the topography. The glycerol stocks of bacteria were incubated at 37 °C in 50 ml of Luria–Bertani medium (LB) overnight. The bacterial suspension obtained was diluted to an optical density, $OD_{600} = 0.2$. The imprinted and smooth PMMA substrates used for control were placed in 12 well-plates and incubated in static conditions with 2 ml of bacteria suspension during 7 h for *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. For *P. aeruginosa* the time was reduced to 5 h to avoid overcrowding of the surface and be able to identify bacteria individually. After the incubation period, the PMMA substrates were gently rinsed using 1× phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) (Fisher Scientific) and stained using Live/Dead® BacLight™ Viability Kit which contains a mixture of SYTO 9 and propidium iodide fluorescent dyes (Molecular Probes) (0.13 μ l of stain diluted in 1 ml Tris-HCl) for 15 min in dark at room temperature. Finally, the PMMA substrates were rinsed with 1× PBS and mounted with BacLight mounting oil for visualization. The substrates were imaged on a fluorescent microscope (Leica). Live and dead bacteria were counted using the Image J image analysis software (NIH Image). Four independent trials with three replicates of each substrate were run.

Bacteria morphology imaging by SEM

After the bacteria incubation period, all substrates were rinsed with 1× PBS prior to carry out the fixing process with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (Sigma-Aldrich) for 15 min. Subsequently, the substrates were rinsed with increasing gradients of 0, 50, 75, 100% ethanol for 5 min each. These substrates were air dried and sputter-coated with a thin layer of gold prior imaging on an Auriga FIB-SEM system (Zeiss).

Cell proliferation assay

HaCaT cells expressing green fluorescent protein (GFP), were cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM, Biowest) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Gibco), 1% L-Glutamine (Biowest) and 1% penicillin–streptomycin (Biowest) at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ atmosphere. The growth and proliferation of HaCaT cells was assessed on smooth PMMA and polystyrene (PS) films and on the moth-eye imprinted topography. Three independent trials with three replicates of each substrate were run. HaCaT cells were seeded at concentration of 20.000 cells ml⁻¹. Cell viability was evaluated by a colorimetric method based on the reduction of Resazurin (blue) to resofurin (pink) due to the metabolic activity of viable cells. A solution of Resazurin salt (Alfa Aesar) was prepared with a concentration of 10 μ g ml⁻¹.

Absorbance was measured during 15 days at 570 and 600 nm using a micro plate reader (H4 Hybrid Multi-Mode Microplate Reader, BioTek).

Cell morphology imaging

HaCaT cells were seeded and cultured on the different substrates, and collected after 10 d. The cells' nuclei were stained using Dapi (Molecular probes) and the expressed GFP was used for cytoplasm visualization. Prior fluorescence imaging, the substrates were rinsed with 1 × PBS and mounted on FluorSave reagent media (CalBiochem). For SEM imaging, the HaCaT cells on the substrates were rinsed with 1× PBS prior to the fixing process with 4% PFA (Sigma-Aldrich) for 15 min. Then the substrates were rinsed in increasing gradients of 0, 50, 75, 100% ethanol for 5 min in each dilution. The substrates were air dried and sputter-coated with a thin layer of gold prior imaging using an Auriga FIB-SEM system (Zeiss).

Cellular morphology analysis

The morphology of the HaCaT cells was studied in terms of cell spread area and elongation. Three independent trials with three replicates of each substrate were analyzed individually using the image analysis software Image J (NIH Image). Elongation was defined as major axis/minor axis as the cells are fitted into an ellipse. Smooth PMMA substrates were used as control.

Results

Moth-eye topography characterization

PMMA was chosen as standard material to fabricate the moth-eye mimetic topography films because it is a polymer approved for medical applications and commonly employed in ophthalmic implants [34]. It is also a commodity plastic used in a wide range of applications. The moth-eye topography produced by nanoimprinting is displayed in figure 1. The SEM (figure 1(A)) and AFM (figure 1(B)) images of the imprinted substrates revealed a topography formed by well-defined nanocones disposed on hexagonal arrangement with dimensions close to those of the natural moth-eye structures [35]. The array of nanocones show a mean height of 350 nm and a feature width of 80 nm on the cap, 250 nm pitch and aspect ratio of 4.3 (figure 1).

Static water contact angle measured on the PMMA moth-eye topography exhibited an average values of $135 \pm 4^\circ$ that is, in the hydrophobic range. To determine whether this hydrophobic character plays a part on the interaction of the topography with cells, we studied the wetting dynamics of a droplet of gelatin solution, which is a cell adhesive protein, a droplet of FBS and a droplet of LB bacteria culture medium on the polymer moth-eye topography. The contact angle of the droplets decreased rapidly in a period of 10 min,

Figure 1. Moth-eye mimetic topography imaging and geometrical characterization by (A) SEM, (B) 3D AFM and (C) AFM cross sectional profile.

and the topography was hydrophilic and completely wetted in 20 min (see supporting information figure S2 (stacks.iop.org/BB/13/026011/mmedia)). This result suggests that when the moth-eye surfaces are placed on a biological medium, the surfaces will be covered with proteins and will turn hydrophilic. Hence, we can assume that cell attachment is not prevented due to the hydrophobic character of the surface as it is lost after several minutes in contact with a protein containing medium.

Bactericidal efficacy of the moth-eye topography

The bactericidal properties of the moth-eye topography were assessed through viability tests of cultured *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* as model of Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria respectively. For this, bacteria were seeded on the imprinted substrates and smooth substrates as control and incubated during specific periods of time. After the culture period, the live and dead attached bacteria were stained and counted from fluorescent microscopy images on the smooth and imprinted PMMA substrates. Figures 2(A), (A'), (B), (B'), (C) and (C') show representative fluorescence microscopy images of the live (green) and dead (red) bacteria respectively observed on the substrates. As it can be seen on the images, the coverage percentage and total amount of bacteria adhered onto the substrates was similar. However, the viability of the three bacteria tested was influenced by the topography. The percentages of dead bacteria attached on control

surfaces were found to be 5% for *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* and 15% for *E. coli*. In contrast, a significant increase of the dead population of bacteria was seen on the moth-eye topographical substrates. On these substrates, the percentage of non-viable bacteria increased up to 55%, 45%, 30% for *S.aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* respectively (figure 2(D)).

Since propidium iodide stains cells with membrane damage although cells may still retain some level of viability, the quantitative results obtained from the Live/Dead® BacLight™ viability assays were verified using the ISO 22196 norm. Following this norm, the fraction of viable bacteria on the substrates was measured as CFUs (Colony Forming Units) counted by the pour plate culture method. Comparable data was obtained by both methods (see supporting information, figure S1) confirming the bactericidal effect of the moth-eye surface for both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. The local interaction and morphology of bacteria cultured on smooth and moth-eye substrates was examined through SEM imaging. The SEM images in figures 2(A'')–(C'') show the morphology of bacteria seeded on the smooth surfaces; the *S. aureus* retained the characteristic cocci shape and the *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* kept their rod-like morphology. Conversely, for the bacteria attached onto the moth-eye topography displayed in figures 2(A'')–(C'') for *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* respectively, it can be seen that some of the bacteria have lost their typical morphology and have adopted a squashed appearance

Figure 2. Bactericidal properties of the moth-eye mimetic topography. Comparative fluorescence imaging of live-dead *S. aureus* ((A) and (A')), *E. coli* ((B) and (B')) and *P. aeruginosa* ((C) and (C')) incubated on pristine PMMA and moth-eye topography. Scale bar 5 μm . Comparative SEM imaging of the bacteria-topography interaction of *S. aureus* ((A'') and (A''')), *E. coli* ((B'') and (B''')) and *P. aeruginosa* ((C'') and (C''')) attached onto pristine PMMA and moth-eye topography. Scale bar 1 μm . Bactericidal effectiveness plots of smooth PMMA and moth-eye topography against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* (D). The statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) after performing t -tests is marked (*) indicating a significant bactericidal difference between the moth-eye topography compared with the smooth controls. Error bars represent the standard deviation.

indicative of membrane damage or rupture with release of the inner content. Similar bacteria morphology has been seen before on bacteria attached to cicada wing [11, 12] and dragonfly wing inspired topographies [7, 9, 15, 23]. The moth-eye mimetic topography studied in this work, having a geometrical dimensions more similar to those of the dragon fly wing, reveals a comparable bactericidal effect.

The influence of the topography on HaCaT cells' morphology was also evaluated comparatively to the smooth PMMA by fluorescence microscopy imaging (figures 3(B) and (B')). The HaCaT cells were collected at the beginning of logarithmic growth phase where cell spreading and elongation were estimated. The HaCaT cells exhibited an extended morphology on the smooth PMMA substrates and moth-eye mimetic topography. Cell spreading (figure 3(C)) and elongation (figure 3(D)) mean values did not reveal significant changes, indicating that the nanostructured surface did not significantly influence the HaCaT cell response.

SEM imaging was used to study the influence of the surface on cell morphology and cell-topography interaction. Figures 3((B'') and (B''')) show the morphology

of HaCaT cells cultured on smooth PMMA and on the moth-eye topography. HaCaT cells appeared forming bunched clusters attached to both smooth PMMA and on to the moth-eye topography and no significant morphological changes were observed on the SEM images which is consistent with the images obtained by fluorescence microscopy.

Discussion

The bactericidal mechanism of natural nanotopographies most accepted and put forward by several authors experimentally [7–20] and theoretically [15, 36–39] has been based on the severe deformation of the bacteria membrane while pursuing a stable attachment onto the nanocone topography leading to a fatal membrane stretching followed by bacteria death. A different bactericidal mechanism has also been proposed based on the combination of strong adhesion between secreted exopolysaccharides (EPS) filled nanopillars and bacteria as well as shear force when immobilized bacterium try to move to find a more favorable surface attachment [40].

Figure 3. Cytocompatibility of moth-eye mimetic topography. (A) HaCaT cell proliferation profile on polystyrene, smooth PMMA and on the moth-eye topography. (B) Fluorescence Imaging ((B) and (B'), scale bar 50 μm) and SEM imaging of ((B'') scale bar 20 μm , (B''') scale bar 2 μm) of HaCaT cells seeded on smooth PMMA and on the moth-eye topography. (C) Cell projected area and (D) cell elongation of HaCaT cells seeded on smooth PMMA and on the moth-eye topography. Error bars represent standard deviation.

These works evidence that the bactericidal effect arises during the surface attachment process. Certainly, topographical surfaces with dense nanostructures of feature size smaller than that of bacteria, initially offer an effective decrease in the contact area available for adhesion. In the case of the moth-eye topography, the contact area fraction corresponding to the top cone surface is approximately 0.2, which effectively means less available surface area and fewer attachment points compared to a flat surface. This situation may not be ideal for stability of bacteria attachment. However, if as a result of the initial bacteria interaction with the surface by attractive forces such as the Lifshitz-Van der Waals on electrostatic forces, bacteria come close to the surface, bacteria adhesion may progress towards a more consolidated and irreversible attachment phase where molecularly mediated binding between specific adhesins is established [41]. This specific attachment provokes the deformation of the bacteria wall and this deformation brings closer molecules from the bacteria membrane to the surface and mimicking a zipper's mechanism, the bacteria wall will deform further as the adhesion points are increased with the increased adhesive force [42]. When the surface as in the case of the moth-eye topography contains nano-

cone features, concomitantly with local membrane deformation, stretching forces would appear on the suspended part of the membrane between nanocones. When the stretching forces reach the critical breaking value beyond the membrane stretching modulus, the bacteria membrane will rupture leading to bacterial cell death [36, 37].

Previous works on biomimetic topographies have demonstrated that the bactericidal efficiency is dependent upon physical parameters such as density, diameter and stiffness of the surface nanostructures and bacteria [18, 20]. However, the adhesion affinity and adhesion strength of different bacteria species and strains would also play a significant role on the bacteria membrane stresses arising during attachment thus, on the bactericidal efficiency obtained. For a given nanotopography, the adhesion strength of different bacteria is determined by the cell wall architecture and the physicochemical attributes such as the biochemical build-up or bacteria appendages. In fact, the initial contact to a surface has been acknowledged as the mechanical cue that triggers intracellular signalling cascades that guide the phenotypic changes and ultimately determine the bacteria attachment strength and eventually their fate [41]. Through pro-

cesses of mechanosensing and transduction, bacteria may generate different biological responses to a surface topography [43, 44]. Some surface-associated behaviours have already been ascribed to mechanosensing, including processes such as EPS production and biofilm formation [45], fimbrial expression [46] and viability [41]. AFM measurements, have demonstrated that surface roughness and topography promote the adhesion of *S. aureus* and increase the adhesion force and work of adhesion with the surface [47, 48]. Hence going forward, while the biocidal mechanism of nanotopographies has been recognized to be of a mechanical origin, many key questions need to be explored related to the mechano-sensing and transduction mechanisms arising from the interaction of bacteria with the nanotopography that may translate onto different biocidal efficiency for different bacteria species and strains.

Despite the huge interest of antibacterial surfaces for medical implants and tissue regeneration, only few works have investigated the impact of bactericidal topographies on eukaryotic cell functions [22, 23, 26, 49].

Many authors have shown that matrix nanotopography is a key factor in the regulation of eukaryotic cell functions such as cell adhesion, spreading, proliferation, migration and differentiation. The mechanical stimulation from nanotopography takes place through the modulation of focal adhesive sites on a substrate as cells can perceive variations of a few nanometers on a surface topography [50, 51]. The results of this study indicate that the isotropic discrete nanocones of the moth-eye topography allowed the HaCat cells to spread in all directions uniformly and no significant deformation of the cell membrane was observed compared to the cells on the flat control substrates indicating that the cells' membrane has conformed to the topography. Indeed, compared to bacteria, keratinocytes are much softer material with a Young's modulus measured as 84.5 KPa and large area stretching modulus in the range of 200–250 mN m⁻¹ [52, 53]. On the other hand, the Young's modulus for Gram-positive bacteria is in the range of 80–95 MPa [54] and for the Gram-negative bacteria is in the range of 10–25 MPa with a stretching modulus about 0.5–2 mN m⁻¹ [55]. Consequently, keratinocyte cells are more adaptive and much more resistant towards mechanical stretching than bacteria, and accordingly the moth-eye topography did not entail a threat to their viability.

Conclusion

In summary, this work describes the bactericidal action of a moth-eye mimetic topography fabricated in polymer via thermal nanoimprinting. This surface has proven to be an effective bactericidal topography against Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. Mechanistically, the results support the theoretical models proposed before where the mechanical rupture

of bacteria by surface nanocone topographies is the result of the stretching force arising on the membrane of bacteria pursuing a stable attachment. Moreover, the cytocompatibility of the moth-eye mimetic topography towards human keratinocytes has been verified. Hence, moth-eye mimetic topography appears to be a promising bactericidal cytocompatible surface which can potentially facilitate the host tissue integration process of implantable devices or resorbable scaffolds for tissue regeneration.

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